

Italian word lists' representativeness of student writing: a corpus-based study

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To what extent can word lists be used as a tool to summarize language for teaching purposes? Word lists have been a research topic for many decades now, but despite their usefulness as a learning tool for students (see e.g. Durrant, 2016), they also have some limitations. One of them is the fact that studying the words using only lists where words are isolated does not give credit to the pedagogical importance of “constellations of words” (Palmer, cited in McArthur, 1998), i.e., words that should be taught together.

Another issue concerns the historically limited availability of student corpora focusing on academic writing (Nesi & Gardner, 2012), giving few possibilities to fully understand student vocabulary choices. This is one possible reason behind the fact that most lists, including academic word lists, are constructed based on the texts that students should read, not those they write. Another factor is that these lists were initially aimed at L2 students; with (advanced) L1 students they could be seen not only as a target to achieve, but also as an instrument to be verified and updated in light of possible language change.

In this paper, I will specifically explore how relevant Italian word lists are for texts written by native speakers, in particular if the words present in the lists are representative of the way young people write. To do this, I will use ITACA (<https://itaca.eurac.edu/>), a corpus of texts written by L1 Italian students in the province of Bolzano. These texts will be profiled by using the Academic Italian Word List (Spina, 2010) and the Vocabolario di base (“Core Vocabulary”, De Mauro, 2015). I expect the results to show differences between the words used by the students and the word lists, leading to the conclusion that academic language is changing.

References

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